

Energy Efficiency and Reliability of Communication Systems Using SCCOD, SCSH, and SCOPT Signal Constellations

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Abstract—This paper presents a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency of communication systems using SCCOD coded signal constellations, Shannon-type SCSH constellations, and a new composite signal constellation referred to as SCOPT. The geometric properties of the corresponding decision regions in Euclidean and Hamming spaces are analyzed together with their influence on message transmission reliability, spectral efficiency, and energy efficiency.

It is shown that among different classes of SCCOD constellations, SCCOD-RS constellations based on Reed–Solomon codes can provide the highest energy efficiency. A comparative analysis of the energy and computational efficiency of SCCOD-RS and SCCOD-LDPC systems is performed.

A method for constructing multidimensional composite SCOPT constellations is proposed. The method is based on the development of Shannon’s idea that the reliability of message transmission can be improved by increasing the duration of multidimensional signals. In contrast to SCSH constellations, whose decision regions have a hyperspherical structure, SCOPT constellations employ composite lower-dimensional decision regions, which substantially simplifies signal generation and demodulation procedures.

It is shown that SCOPT constellations make it possible to provide highly reliable transmission while transmitting only information symbols through the communication channel and may, under certain conditions, provide lower required SNR and higher energy efficiency than SCSH constellations.

The work has an engineering-theoretical orientation and is focused on practical approaches to improving the energy efficiency of communication systems while maintaining high transmission reliability and acceptable computational complexity of demodulators and decoders. The obtained results may be of interest for the development of advanced communication systems, including systems with high spectral efficiency, multipath channels, and MIMO systems.

Keywords—communication theory; signal constellations; coded modulation; energy efficiency; spectral efficiency; transmission reliability; error-correcting codes; multidimensional modulation; Shannon limit.

I. INTRODUCTION

The enormous importance of the telecommunications industry for modern civilization is confirmed by the rapid growth of global Internet traffic, including fixed networks, data centers, and Wi-Fi networks. According to the International Telecommunication Union, this growth has reached approximately 25–30% annually in recent years. According to Ericsson, global mobile traffic by the end of 2025 reached approximately 200 EB per month (1 EB = 10^{18} bytes).

From an engineering viewpoint, the development of telecommunications has resulted in the large-scale deployment of fifth-generation (5G) mobile communication systems and preparations for the transition to 6G systems, the widespread implementation of fiber-optic communication lines, increasing densities of base stations, and growing energy consumption of data centers.

The main objectives in the development of communication systems are to provide highly reliable message transmission together with high energy and spectral efficiency.

The active development of telecommunications began more than a century ago [1]. However, the scientific foundations of modern communication theory were formulated only in the middle of the twentieth century. A decisive role in this process was played by the works of C. Shannon [2] and V. A. Kotelnikov [3].

In Shannon's fundamental works, the basic principles of information theory and message transmission were formulated. These works investigated methods for reducing message redundancy, determined the fundamental limits of information compression, and established the conditions for reliable transmission over noisy communication channels.

In information theory, a message is represented as a sequence of symbols $\vec{X}(x_1, \dots, x_{N_c})$, transmitted through a discrete communication channel in which a symbol x_i may, with probability p_{ij} , be distorted and replaced by a symbol x_j . Shannon showed that if k information symbols are selected from the sequence, each capable of assuming U different values, and supplemented by r parity symbols related to the information symbols through specific mathematical relations, then the set of $M = U^k$ such sequences forms a code.

Each sequence in this set represents a codeword (CW). The structure of the codewords can be chosen such that, when a portion of the symbols is distorted, their values can be recovered, thereby ensuring reliable message reception.

In [2], Shannon also proposed a method for determining the capacity of a discrete communication channel with known transition probabilities p_{ij} . In addition, he investigated the conditions for reliable message transmission over continuous communication channels in which the sequence \vec{X} is transmitted using specific signal constellations.

The problem of reliable message transmission over a continuous Gaussian channel was considered by Shannon in [4], [5]. In these works, it was shown that by using special signal constellations, hereinafter referred to as SCSH constellations, it is possible to transmit only information symbols while achieving arbitrarily high transmission

reliability. Transmission reliability is characterized by the demodulation error probability P_{dem} , defined as the probability that at least one information symbol of the message is received incorrectly during the demodulation of signals $S_m(t)$ belonging to the SCSH constellation.

In [2]–[5], the signals $S_m(t)$ were considered as signal points in an N -dimensional Euclidean space. If the signals have duration T and occupy bandwidth F , then the dimensionality of the signal space is $N = 2n$, where $n = FT$ is an integer representing the normalized signal duration [6].

Gaussian noise arriving at the demodulator input together with the signal can be represented by the vector $\mathbf{U}_n = (n_1, n_2 \dots n_N)$, whose components are independent normalized Gaussian random variables with zero mean and variance 0.5. Under the action of noise, the signal point is displaced in the signal space by an amount $|\mathbf{U}_n| = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N n_i^2}$.

The parameters of a signal constellation must be chosen such that the values of the information symbols can be determined in the demodulator with a high probability of correct reception despite the presence of noise. In modern communication systems, the required error probability is typically on the order of $P_{dem} = 10^{-6} \dots 10^{-10}$.

According to [4], [5], one of the principal objectives in constructing SCSH constellations is to maximize the minimum Euclidean distance (MED) between neighboring signals $S_{m1}(t)$ and $S_{m2}(t)$, defined as $D_E(P_s, R_f) = \sqrt{\int_0^T [S_{m1}(t) - S_{m2}(t)]^2 dt}$. Here, P_s is the average transmitter power, and R_f is the spectral efficiency of the communication system, equal to the message transmission rate normalized to the channel bandwidth. At the receiver side, the parameter P_s is usually replaced by the signal-to-noise ratio ρ_s measured at the demodulator input.

In [4], Shannon proved his well-known coding theorem, according to which it is possible to construct SCSH constellations whose minimum Euclidean distance increases proportionally to \sqrt{n} . It follows that, as the normalized signal duration increases ($n \rightarrow \infty$), the error probability satisfies $P_{dem} \rightarrow 0$ provided that the signal-to-noise ratio satisfies the condition $\rho_s > \rho_{s0}$, where $\rho_{s0} = 2^{R_f} - 1$. The quantity ρ_{s0}

corresponding to a given spectral efficiency R_f is commonly referred to in communication theory as the Shannon limit.

Shannon's results [2], [4], [5], which introduced the fundamental concepts of communication theory, investigated methods for reducing message redundancy, and established the fundamental limits of reliable information transmission over discrete and continuous channels, had a decisive influence on the development of modern communication and signal-processing systems.

At the same time, Shannon's works were primarily fundamental in nature. They established the theoretical possibility of constructing communication systems with specified characteristics; however, specific engineering methods for implementing such systems were not proposed.

As noted by Gallager [7], "Shannon frequently said that he was not particularly interested in applications, but rather was interested in good or interesting problems." Nevertheless, Shannon's works stimulated the development of numerous engineering directions in communication and coding theory aimed at the practical implementation of the principles he proposed.

One of the most important directions in the development of communication theory became coding theory, which was based on Shannon's results [2]. Within this framework, numerous error-correcting codes providing high transmission reliability were developed. The fundamental principles of coding theory are presented, in particular, in [6], [8].

On the basis of various codes, coded signal constellations were developed, which hereinafter will be referred to as SCCOD constellations. Such constellations were widely used in communication systems throughout the twentieth century. For transmitting the symbols of codewords in SCCOD systems, basic signal constellations including quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), amplitude phase shift modulation (APSM), and hexagonal modulation (HEXM) were employed [6].

For two-dimensional constellations, the minimum Euclidean distance between neighboring signals is relatively small. For QAM constellations, for example, $D_E(\rho_s, R_f) = \sqrt{3 \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}} \right)}$, where ρ_s is the signal-to-noise ratio at the

demodulator input, and $\rho_{so} = 2^{R_f} - 1$ is the Shannon limit corresponding to the spectral efficiency R_f of the constellation. The spectral efficiency is given by $R_f = \log_2(M_m)$ bit/(s·Hz), where M_m is the number of signals in the QAM constellation.

When such signals are demodulated, the symbol error probability $p_{er}(\rho_s)$ generally remains relatively large and may be on the order of $p_{er}(\rho_s) \approx 0.1$.

In the construction of SCCOD constellations, an important engineering problem arises. On the one hand, it is necessary to select a code capable of providing growth of the minimum Euclidean distance between signals proportional to $\sqrt{N_c}$, where N_c is the codeword length, similarly to SCSH constellations. On the other hand, the selected code should allow sufficiently simple implementation of encoding and decoding algorithms.

In this paper, a method for constructing optimal SCCOD constellations providing large minimum Euclidean distances between signals is considered. It is shown that the most effective constellations are those based on Reed–Solomon codes [6], [8]. Such constellations are hereinafter referred to as SCCOD-RS. It is shown that, for a given spectral efficiency, SCCOD-RS constellations exhibit the minimum energy losses relative to SCSH constellations.

The paper also presents a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency of communication systems using SCCOD constellations, SCSH constellations, and a new signal constellation referred to as SCOPT. As shown in [9], under certain assumptions SCOPT constellations may provide higher energy efficiency than SCSH constellations.

Section II considers the structure and parameters of optimal SCCOD constellations, together with methods for signal demodulation and evaluation of transmission reliability. Section III provides a brief description of SCSH and SCOPT constellations. Section IV presents the results of a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency of different communication systems. Section V contains an estimate of the possible economic effect associated with reducing the energy consumption of the global communication infrastructure through the use of energy-efficient signal

constellations. Finally, Section VI summarizes the main conclusions of the paper.

II. MAIN PROPERTIES OF SCCOD CONSTELLATIONS

For the transmission of codeword (CW) symbols, which may be represented by the vector $\vec{X}(x_1, \dots, x_k, x_{k+1}, \dots, x_{N_c})$, basic signal constellations such as QAM, APSM, and HEXM are employed. The principal parameters of a code are the code rate $R_c = \frac{k}{N_c}$, and the minimum Hamming distance between codewords $D_c(N_c, R_c)$, which is equal to the minimum number of differing symbols between any two codewords of the code [6], [8].

Codewords may be regarded as individual signals of an SCCOD constellation. In this case, the minimum Euclidean distance between signals is determined by the expression [10]

$$\sqrt{D_{EC}(\rho_s, R_f, R_c)} = \sqrt{D_E(\rho_s, R_f) D_c(N_c, R_c)} \quad , \quad \text{where}$$

$\sqrt{D_E(\rho_s, R_f)}$ is the minimum Euclidean distance between the signals of the basic constellation, and $D_c(N_c, R_c)$ is the minimum Hamming distance of the code.

It should be noted that the spectral efficiency of SCCOD constellations, $R_{fc} = R_f R_c < R_f$, is always lower than the spectral efficiency of the basic constellation used for transmitting codeword symbols.

High energy efficiency of SCCOD constellations can be achieved only if the minimum Hamming distance $D_c(N_c, R_c)$ increases proportionally to the codeword length N_c . Such a property is characteristic only of a limited class of codes. The most efficient codes in this respect are maximum distance separable (MDS) codes, for which $D_c(N_c, R_c) = N_c(1 - R_c)$.

Among linear block codes, Reed–Solomon (RS) codes are well known for achieving the Singleton bound and providing the maximum possible minimum Hamming distance for a given number of parity symbols [6], [8].

In linear codes, the r parity symbols are related to the k information symbols by a system of Diophantine equations $x_i = \sum_{l=1}^k h_{li} x_l$, $i = k + 1, \dots, N_c$, which can be written in matrix form as

$$\vec{X}_r = \mathbf{H} \vec{X}_k \quad (1)$$

Here, $\mathbf{H} = \|h_{li}\|$ is a $k \times r$ matrix, $\vec{X}_k = (x_1, \dots, x_k)$ is the vector of information symbols, and $\vec{X}_r = (x_{k+1}, \dots, x_{N_c})$ is the vector of parity symbols.

For RS codes, the matrix \mathbf{H} may be constructed using Vandermonde, Fourier, circulant, and other classes of matrices. In practical communication systems, Vandermonde matrices are most commonly used [11], [12].

For RS codes, the minimum Hamming distance is equal to the number of parity symbols, $D_c(N_c, R_c) = r$, whereas for codes outside the MDS class the minimum Hamming distance is generally smaller than r .

It is well known that, under hard-decision decoding, a code with minimum Hamming distance $D_c(N_c, R_c)$ can correct $T_c = 0.5D_c(N_c, R_c)$ errors within a codeword. Under soft-decision decoding, where the reliability of the demodulator decisions is evaluated together with the symbol values, the number of correctable errors increases and may reach $D_{un} = [D_c(N_c, R_c) - 1]$. The features of hard- and soft-decision decoding are discussed in greater detail below.

A. Selection of Codeword Length in SCCOD

Any error-correcting code possesses only a limited error-correction capability. Therefore, in order to ensure high transmission reliability, the number of errors in a codeword of length N_c must not exceed the correction capability of the employed code. The codeword length must be selected such that the probability that the number of erroneously received symbols in the sequence $\vec{X}(x_1, \dots, x_k, x_{k+1}, \dots, x_{N_c})$ exceeds a permissible value D_{er} remains sufficiently small.

At the same time, the code must guarantee correction of all errors provided that their number does not exceed D_{er} . The probability of such an event determines the message demodulation error probability P_{dem} .

Let $p_{er}(\rho_s)$ denote the probability of erroneous reception of a single codeword symbol, and let N_{er} denote the number of erroneously received symbols in a CW. Since N_{er} follows a binomial distribution, the probability that $N_{er} \geq D_{er}$ is given by $P_{dem}(N_c, p_{er}) = \sum_{i=D_{er}}^{N_c} C_{N_c}^i p_{er}^i (1 - p_{er})^{N_c - i}$. Using the Chernoff bound [6], we obtain the following approximation:

$$P_{dem}(N_c, p_{er}) \cong \begin{cases} e^{-N_c \Omega(\gamma, d_{er}, p_{er})} & \text{for } \left(\frac{d_{er}}{p_{er}}\right) > 1 \\ 1 & \text{for } \left(\frac{d_{er}}{p_{er}}\right) \leq 1 \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where $d_{er} = \left(\frac{D_{er}}{N_c}\right)$, $\gamma = \left(\frac{d_{er}}{p_{er}}\right)$, and $\Omega(\gamma, d_{er}, p_{er}) = [d_{er} \ln(\gamma) + (1 - d_{er}) \ln\left(\frac{1-d_{er}}{1-p_{er}}\right)]$.

For basic QAM constellations, the symbol error probability is determined by $p_{er}(\rho_s) = 2Q(\sqrt{V})$, where $Q(x) = \int_x^\infty e^{-0.5y^2} \frac{dy}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$ and $V = 3\left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}}\right)$, with $\rho_{so} = (2^{R_f} - 1)$ representing the Shannon limit for the basic QAM constellation.

For soft-decision decoding, the code used in SCCOD must be capable of correcting at least D_{er} errors, i.e., it must satisfy the condition $D_c(N_c, R_c) \geq D_{er}$.

It follows from (2) that the dependence of the error probability $P_{dem}(N_c, p_{er})$ on the parameter $p_{er}(\rho_s)$ has a threshold character. The error probability can decrease with increasing codeword length only if the signal-to-noise ratio satisfies the condition $\rho_s > \rho_{sc}$, where ρ_{sc} is an analogue of the Shannon limit for SCCOD and is determined by the equation $p_{er}(\rho_s) = d_{er}$.

The parameter d_{er} depends on the minimum Hamming distance of the particular code on which the SCCOD constellation is based.

In this respect, the geometric properties of SCCOD and SCSH constellations exhibit a certain similarity. In both cases, the decision region has a spherical structure. For SCSH constellations, this region represents a hypersphere in Euclidean space [4], [5], whereas for SCCOD constellations the analogous region is formed in Hamming space.

The codeword length required to achieve a specified error probability is determined by

$$N_c(\gamma) = \frac{\ln(1/P_{dem})}{\Omega(\gamma, d_{er}, p_{er})}. \quad (3)$$

It follows from (2) that when $\gamma \approx 1$, very large values of N_c are required to achieve high transmission reliability. Therefore, in practical systems, the signal-to-noise ratio should be chosen such that the condition $\frac{d_c}{p_{er}(\rho_s)} > 2$, is satisfied, where $d_c = \frac{D_c(N_c, R_c)}{N_c}$.

It should be noted that expressions (2) and (3) are valid for arbitrary SCCOD constellations, including constellations

based on RS, LDPC, concatenated, convolutional, and other types of codes. It also follows from (3) that the required codeword length decreases as the parameter γ increases. For RS codes, $D_c(N_c, R_c) = N_c(1 - R_c)$, and therefore $\gamma = \frac{1-R_c}{p_{er}(\rho_s)}$.

The relationships associated with the selection of SCCOD parameters in the design of communication systems are further discussed in Section V.

B. Demodulation of SCCOD Signals

Demodulation of signals in communication systems employing SCCOD constellations includes two interrelated procedures: demodulation of the basic constellation signals and decoding of the codewords belonging to the employed code.

In communication systems of the mid-twentieth century, hard-decision decoding was predominantly used. In this approach, the demodulator generated only estimates of the received symbol values without taking into account their reliability. Some of these estimates could be erroneous, and algebraic decoding methods were employed for error correction [7], [8].

These methods were based on algebraic coding theory and finite-field algebra and included two successive procedures: determination of the positions of erroneously received symbols and subsequent correction of their values.

For error localization, a syndrome was calculated, after which a nonlinear Diophantine equation was formed. Solving this equation made it possible to determine the positions of erroneous symbols within the codeword. The erroneous symbol values were then recovered by solving a system of linear Diophantine equations of the form (1), whose order was determined by the number of correctable errors T_c .

Algebraic methods are mainly applicable to hard-decision decoding [13]. When the number of errors becomes large, their practical implementation becomes rather complex. For this reason, coding theory actively developed methods oriented toward simpler decoding procedures.

It should be noted that in classical algebraic decoding methods, the features of signal processing in the demodulator of the basic constellation were taken into account only to a limited extent.

Apparently, one of the earliest works proposing a simple soft-decision decoding algorithm that incorporates symbol reliability information was [14]. In [14], reception of codewords of the simplest Wagner code was considered, in which one parity symbol was added to a binary sequence of information symbols to ensure that the modulo-two sum of all symbols was equal to zero.

During demodulation, this condition was checked. If the condition was violated, the reliability of the decisions regarding the received symbol values was evaluated. Reliability was evaluated by comparing the voltage at the output of the synchronous detector with the decision threshold. The least reliable symbol was considered to be the one whose distance to the threshold was minimal. The value of this symbol was then inverted. It was shown in [14] that such a method provides higher reception reliability than the use of a Hamming code correcting a single error by algebraic methods.

A more general approach extending the ideas of [14] was proposed in [10]. In this method, the displacement of the symbol estimate caused by noise is related to the likelihood ratio associated with the symbol. In the absence of noise, no displacement occurs and the decisions produced by the demodulator are error-free. Consequently, the magnitude of the displacement makes it possible to classify symbol estimates into more reliable and less reliable groups.

Since every code is capable of correcting only a limited number of errors, it is expedient in the demodulator to divide the codeword symbols into two groups. It is well known [6], [8] that algebraic decoding methods can correct errors provided that their number does not exceed $T_c = \frac{D_c(N_c, R_c)}{2}$.

Therefore, the demodulator may identify a group of T_c least reliable symbols together with a group of symbols whose values are determined with high reliability. The values of the unreliable symbols are then reconstructed by solving the system of equations (1), in which the reliably determined symbols are treated as known quantities.

It is also known that under maximum-likelihood decoding the number of correctable errors may approach $D_{un} = [D_c(N_c, R_c) - 1]$ [6], [8]. In this case, the demodulator

identifies a group of D_{un} least reliable symbols whose values are also determined by solving the system of equations (1).

Under such an approach, the demodulator becomes functionally integrated with the decoder [10], since it simultaneously performs reliability estimation of the received symbols and reconstruction of the values of all symbols classified as unreliable.

As a result, the decoding procedure is reduced to solving a system of Diophantine equations relating the information and parity symbols.

The described approach is applicable to SCCOD constellations constructed on the basis of a broad class of linear codes [10]. Consider the decoding procedure in the case where, under soft-decision decoding, unreliable symbols $Z_j, j=1 \dots D_{un}$, have been identified in the codeword.

If the values of the reliably determined symbols are substituted into (1) and the known terms are transferred to the right-hand side, the following system of Diophantine equations is obtained:

$$\sum_{l=1}^{D_{un}} H_{li} Z_l = Y_i, \quad (4)$$

where the quantities Y_i and the elements of the matrix $\mathbf{H}_{un} = \|H_{li}\|$ of dimension $D_{un} \times D_{un}$ are known. The computational complexity of solving system (4) is proportional to $N_a = (D_{un})^2$.

The solution of such Diophantine equations is in several respects analogous to solving systems of linear equations over the field of real numbers. At present, software tools capable of efficiently solving high-order systems of such equations have been developed and are available. These methods may be employed in the construction of communication-system decoders.

At the decoder input, the demodulator supplies the indices of the symbols whose values have been determined unreliably, while the decoder output generates the sequence of information symbols defining the received message. If the codeword length is relatively small, the computational complexity of such decoding does not represent a significant practical problem.

It should also be noted that a conceptually similar method for identifying unreliable symbols was proposed in [15] for decoding concatenated codes. In that method, two thresholds

are used in the demodulator to form an uncertainty region for the received decisions. If the voltage at the output of the synchronous detector falls within this region, the decision concerning the corresponding symbol is regarded as unreliable. A disadvantage of the method proposed in [15] is that decoding becomes impossible if the number of unreliable symbols exceeds D_{un} . Moreover, if the number of such symbols is smaller than D_{un} , algebraic decoding methods are still required for their localization and correction.

Let us briefly consider several soft-decision decoding methods employed in communication systems with SCCOD constellations [6], [13], [16].

A significant number of such methods are based on the calculation of likelihood ratios for the received symbols. One of the best-known approaches is the Chase algorithm, which is based on generating a list of the most probable codewords. From this list, the codeword having the minimum Euclidean distance from the sequence applied to the demodulator input is selected. The performance of this method may approach maximum-likelihood decoding [13]. However, the computational complexity of the Chase algorithm increases rapidly with increasing codeword length, since the number of candidate sequences becomes very large.

To reduce decoding complexity, low-density parity-check (LDPC) codes and turbo codes were developed. Their decoding is based on the iterative belief propagation (BP) algorithm, which typically requires approximately 10–50 iterations. Owing to their comparatively moderate computational complexity, such codes have found widespread application in modern communication systems.

It should also be noted that a number of codes and coded modulation schemes have been specifically designed to simplify decoding procedures. These include majority-logic codes, trellis-coded modulation (TCM), multilevel coded modulation (MLCM), and bit-interleaved coded modulation (BICM) [6].

In coding theory, code efficiency is often evaluated through the relationship between minimum Hamming distance and code rate [7], [8], [13]. Codes whose characteristics lie below the Varshamov–Gilbert bound are generally regarded as insufficiently efficient for practical applications. For LDPC

codes, these dependencies are located somewhat above this bound [8], [17].

MDS codes, including Reed–Solomon codes, form the upper region of such diagram. For all other codes and coded modulation schemes, the minimum Hamming distance is smaller than that of SCCOD-RS constellations.

Section V shows that, when SCCOD-RS constellations are employed, the implementation complexity of demodulators may be lower than that of other SCCOD types.

III. MAIN PROPERTIES OF SCSH AND SCOPT CONSTELLATIONS

In Shannon’s work [4], fundamental results were obtained demonstrating the theoretical possibility of achieving arbitrarily high transmission reliability while transmitting only information symbols through the communication channel.

Shannon also showed that high reliability can be achieved without increasing transmitter power, solely by increasing the signal duration in multidimensional signal constellations. In the present paper, such constellations are referred to as SCSH constellations.

Although Shannon did not propose specific methods for the generation and demodulation of SCSH signals, he identified their most important geometric properties. In particular, the decision region of SCSH signals has the form of a multidimensional sphere. It is precisely this property that underlies Shannon’s theorem, according to which reliable communication at spectral efficiency R_f is possible only under the condition $\rho_s > \rho_{so}$, where $\rho_{so} = 2^{R_f} - 1$ is the Shannon limit.

It should be noted that this theorem effectively applies to communication systems employing signal constellations with spherical decision regions. As noted in the previous section, SCCOD constellations possess similar geometric properties. For such systems, the dependence of the error probability on the signal-to-noise ratio has a pronounced threshold character.

Shannon’s theorem played an exceptionally important role in the development of communication theory and communication engineering, since it demonstrated the possibility of substantially increasing the energy efficiency of

communication systems by increasing signal duration. However, SCSH-type constellations providing transmission of only information symbols have not been reported to date.

To achieve high transmission reliability, various SCCOD constellations have been developed in modern communication systems, in which both information and parity symbols are transmitted. Systems employing very long codewords, reaching tens of thousands of symbols, have been developed and are capable of providing extremely low message error probabilities.

However, as noted in Section II, the transmission of parity symbols generally leads to a reduction in both energy and spectral efficiency. For many practical SCCOD systems, the energy loss relative to the Shannon limit is typically on the order of 4–7 dB at $R_f > 5$ bit/(s·Hz).

It should also be noted that the widely used two-dimensional constellations QAM, APSK, and HEXM were introduced after the publication of Shannon’s works [4], [5]. The geometric properties of these constellations differ substantially from those of SCSH and SCCOD constellations. In such constellations, the decision region of each signal is represented by a Voronoi polygon containing all points of the signal space nearest to the corresponding signal point.

Consider a composite N -dimensional signal intended for the transmission of only information symbols and consisting of n two-dimensional signals, where $N = 2n$.

In this case, the decision region of the N -dimensional signal is also decomposed into n independent two-dimensional regions. Each such region corresponds to two signal coordinates defining two information symbols of the transmitted message.

Under the action of noise, the signal coordinates are displaced in the N -dimensional space. However, if the noise components are statistically independent, decisions regarding each pair of coordinates may be made independently of the remaining signal coordinates.

This substantially simplifies the demodulation procedure compared with SCSH and SCCOD constellations, where signal processing has a significantly more multidimensional character.

In this section, a method for constructing composite N -dimensional signal constellations, hereinafter referred to as SCOPT constellations, is considered. This approach is based on Shannon’s idea of increasing the minimum Euclidean distance between signals by increasing their duration. As shown below, the use of N -dimensional SCOPT constellations based on this idea may provide a substantial improvement in energy efficiency under certain conditions.

A. SCSH Constellations

This section briefly reviews a method for evaluating transmission reliability in communication systems employing SCSH constellations. A more detailed description of this method is given in [9], where it is shown that the condition for an error event in the reception of SCSH signals may be written as

$$z = (\sum_{i=1}^N n_i^2) \geq D_E(\rho_s, \rho_{so}, n)/4 = n(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}}), \quad (6)$$

Here, n_i are independent Gaussian noise components. Condition (6) follows from the fact that the decision region associated with SCSH signals has the form of a hypersphere of radius \sqrt{n} .

The probability of satisfying condition (6) is determined by $P_{dem}(\rho_s, R_f, n) = \int_{n(\rho_s/\rho_{so})}^{\infty} p_n(z) dz$. Using the Chernoff method [6], an accurate approximation for this probability may be obtained:

$$P_{dem}(\rho_s, R_f, n) \cong \begin{cases} \exp[-ny(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}})] & \text{for } \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}} > 1 \\ 1 & \text{for } \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}} \leq 1 \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where $y(\rho_s, \rho_{so}) = (\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}}) - 1 - \ln(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_{so}})$.

It follows from (7) that for $\rho_s > \rho_{so}$ and $n \rightarrow \infty$, the error probability tends to zero: $P_{dem}(\rho_s, \rho_{so}, n) \rightarrow 0$, which corresponds to Shannon’s theorem. Expression (7) exhibits a pronounced threshold behavior. When $\rho_s \leq \rho_{so}$, the error probability remains close to unity, whereas for $\rho_s > \rho_{so}$ it decreases rapidly with increasing normalized signal duration n .

It should also be noted that when $\rho_s = \rho_{so}$, we obtain $P_{dem}(\rho_s, R_f, n) = 0.5$. The parameter ρ_{so} , referred to as the Shannon limit, is traditionally used for comparing the energy efficiency of various communication systems with an “ideal”

Shannon system. However, it should be taken into account that practical implementations of SCSH systems simultaneously providing transmission of only information symbols and arbitrarily high reliability have not been widely reported.

Therefore, comparison of practical communication systems with such an “idealized” model is, to some extent, conditional. Moreover, at $\rho_s = \rho_{so}$, SCSH systems do not provide reliable communication.

An important feature of SCSH constellations is that the condition for correct reception given by (6) is determined by the total noise energy over all signal coordinates. This means that the reception decision must be based on processing the entire N -dimensional signal. Such a procedure generally requires more complex demodulation compared with systems in which individual coordinates may be processed independently.

B. SCOPT Constellations

This section briefly **reviews** the structure of SCOPT signal constellations, which are described in greater detail in [9]. Signals belonging to N -dimensional SCOPT constellations may be represented in the form

$$S_m(t) = \sqrt{n_K \rho_s} [\sum_l^q S_{ml}(t)]. \quad (8)$$

Here, $S_m(t)$ denotes a composite signal consisting of q component signals $S_{m_l}(t)$, $l = 1 \dots q$, each having dimensionality $2K$. In this case, $N = 2n_K$ and $n_K = qK$. The component signals are represented as $S_{m_l}(t) = [\sum_{i=1}^{2K} x_{(l-1)q+i}^m V_{(l-1)q+i}(t)]$, where $V_{(l-1)q+i}(t)$ are elementary orthogonal signals used for transmitting the information symbols $x_{(l-1)q+i}^m$ [9]. The normalized signals

$$\hat{S}_m(t) = \frac{S_m(t)}{\sqrt{\rho_s n_K}} \text{ and } S_{m_l}(t) \text{ have unit average power.}$$

The signal coordinates take the values $x_{(l-1)q+i}^m(l) = 0.5d_E[2(i-K)-1]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2K$, lying within the interval $x_{(l-1)q+i}^m(l) \in [-0.5d_E(2K-1); 0.5d_E(2K-1)]$.

Each signal $S_{m_l}(t)$ contains $2K$ coordinates separated by the value d_E , which represents the normalized Euclidean distance between adjacent coordinates. Different signals $S_{m_l}(t)$ are formed by permutations of coordinate values. The number of such permutations is $M_{sl} = (2K)!$, which corresponds to the number of signals in each $2K$ -dimensional

component constellation. The total number of signals in the complete constellation is thus $M = (M_{sl})^q$. The spectral efficiency of SCOPT is determined by

$$R_f(K) = \frac{\log_2(M)}{Kq} = \frac{\log_2[(2K)!]}{K}. \quad (9)$$

The important difference between SCOPT and SCSH constellations is that only a single noise component n_i affects each signal coordinate. Accordingly, the condition for erroneous reception of an individual coordinate may be written as

$$|n_i| \geq \frac{\sqrt{D_E(\rho_s, R_f, n_K)}}{2}. \quad (10)$$

The message error probability is determined by the probability that at least one signal coordinate falls outside its corresponding decision region. It should be noted that condition (10) has the same form as the error condition for QAM signals.

Consequently, the computational complexity of SCOPT demodulation is approximately linear with respect to the number of signal coordinates. As a result, communication systems employing SCOPT constellations may exhibit implementation complexity comparable to that of uncoded QAM systems.

The important parameter of SCOPT constellations is the minimum Euclidean distance between signals. As discussed by Shannon [4], [5], increasing the signal duration makes it possible to increase the minimum Euclidean distance and thereby improve transmission reliability. In [9], it was shown that for SCOPT constellations the minimum Euclidean distance increases proportionally to $\sqrt{n_K}$.

As a result, for SCOPT we obtain

$$\sqrt{D_E(\rho_s, R_f, n_K)} = \sqrt{n_K \rho_s} d_E = \sqrt{\frac{6n_K \rho_s}{(4K^2-1)}}. \quad (11)$$

It follows from (11) that, for a fixed value of K , increasing the parameter q leads to an increase in the normalized signal duration and to an increase in the minimum Euclidean distance proportional to \sqrt{q} . Consequently, the transmission reliability of SCOPT constellations may be improved by increasing the signal duration without requiring an increase in transmitter power.

Unlike SCSH constellations, this property of SCOPT is not directly associated with the constraint $\rho_s > \rho_{so}$. For SCSH

constellations, reliable communication generally cannot be ensured for finite signal durations when $\rho_s \leq \rho_{so}$, whereas for SCOPT constellations high reliability may, under certain conditions, be achieved at low signal-to-noise ratios by increasing the signal duration.

The error probability of SCOPT signals may be expressed as [6] $P_{dem}(\rho_s, R_f, n_K) = 1 - [1 - 2Q(\sqrt{D_E}/2)]^{2n_K}$, where $Q(x) = \int_x^\infty e^{-0.5y^2} \frac{dy}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$ is the Gaussian Q-function. For large values of n_K and small values of $Q(\sqrt{D_E}/2)$, the following approximation may be obtained:

$$P_{dem}(\rho_s, R_f, n_K) \cong 4n_K Q(\sqrt{D_E}/2). \quad (12)$$

In the next section, expressions (2), (7), and (12) are used to perform a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency of communication systems employing SCCOD, SCSH, and SCOPT constellations.

IV. ANALYSIS OF THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS USING SCCOD, SCSH, AND SCOPT CONSTELLATIONS

At various stages in the development of communication systems, different SCCOD constellations based on LDPC, turbo, concatenated, convolutional, polar, and other coding schemes, have been employed and continue to be employed.

A common property of SCCOD constellations is that the increase in the minimum Euclidean distance between signals is achieved by introducing not only information symbols but also parity symbols into the codewords. Increasing the number of parity symbols makes it possible to increase the minimum distance between signals; however, it simultaneously reduces the code rate and therefore decreases the spectral efficiency of the communication system.

The development of numerous codes and coded modulation schemes was associated with the fact that, according to Shannon's results [2], high transmission reliability can be achieved when signals of large duration are employed. However, increasing the codeword length also leads to increased computational complexity of encoding and decoding. This circumstance historically limited the application of SCCOD-RS constellations, since the complexity of demodulation and decoding of Reed–Solomon coded signals increases with increasing codeword length.

At the same time, coding theory shows that, for a given code rate, RS codes possess a very large normalized minimum Hamming distance and achieve the Singleton bound. Other practical codes and coded modulation schemes generally exhibit smaller values of this parameter. Therefore, to achieve the same transmission reliability, the required codeword length for SCCOD-RS constellations may be substantially smaller than for SCCOD constellations based on other codes.

As a consequence, when the same transmission reliability is provided, the total complexity of demodulation and decoding for SCCOD-RS systems may be lower than that of systems employing other SCCOD types.

Fig. 1 presents the dependences $P_{dem}(\rho_s)$ for SCCOD-RS and SCCOD-LDPC constellations calculated using expression (2). It is assumed that transmission of the codewords is performed using basic QAM constellations with spectral efficiency $R_f=6$ bit/(sec·Hz). For the RS and LDPC codes considered in Fig. 1, the code rates are $R_c=0.75, 0.85,$ and 0.9 . Consequently, the spectral efficiencies of the corresponding SCCOD constellations are $R_{fc} = R_f R_c = 5.4, 5.1,$ and 4.5 bit/(s·Hz), respectively. The normalized signal durations for SCCOD-RS and SCCOD-LDPC differ substantially: for SCCOD-RS, $n = 250$, whereas for SCCOD-LDPC, $n = 10000$. Such a large signal duration for SCCOD-LDPC is associated with the comparatively smaller normalized minimum Hamming distance of practical LDPC codes relative to RS codes.

For LDPC codes, this parameter lies near the Varshamov–Gilbert bound defining the region of codes suitable for practical application in communication systems [17].

The results presented in Fig. 1 indicate that, when high transmission reliability $P_{dem}(\rho_s)=10^{-10}$ is required, the use of SCCOD-RS constellations may reduce the required transmitter power by approximately 1 dB compared with SCCOD-LDPC for $R_c = 0.75$ or 0.85 . For $R_c = 0.9$, the required transmitter powers for SCCOD-RS and SCCOD-LDPC systems become approximately equal.

Let us estimate the computational complexity of Reed–Solomon decoding. In the considered case, the codeword length is $N_c=250$, while the numbers of parity symbols for

$R_c = 0.75, 0.85,$ and 0.9 are respectively $r = 62, 37,$ and 25 . As noted in Section II.B, the decoding complexity may be estimated as proportional to $N_a = (D_{un})^2 = (r)^2$. Consequently, for RS codes we obtain $N_a \approx 3800, 1400,$ and 600 for $R_c = 0.75, 0.85,$ and 0.9 , respectively.

For LDPC codes employing the Min-Sum algorithm, the decoding complexity for the same code rates is approximately $N_a = 7 \cdot 10^6, 5 \cdot 10^6$ and $4 \cdot 10^6$. Thus, the computational complexity of LDPC decoding may be significantly higher than that of RS codes under the considered assumptions.

Fig. 1. Dependences of $P_{dem}(\rho_s)$ for SCCOD-RS and SCCOD-LDPC constellations.

It should also be noted that the error probability $P_{dem}(\rho_s)=10^{-10}$ for SCCOD-RS constellations is obtained at symbol error probabilities $p_{er}=0.17, 0.08,$ and 0.04 for code rates $R_c=0.75, 0.85,$ and 0.9 , respectively. In these cases, the required signal-to-noise ratio exceeds the corresponding Shannon limit for SCCOD-RS by approximately 2.7, 3, and 3.4 dB, respectively.

It should be emphasized that similar relationships may also be expected for SCCOD constellations constructed on the basis of practical codes and coded modulation schemes that do not belong to the MDS class. An important practical conclusion therefore follows: in communication systems operating over Gaussian channels and employing SCCOD constellations, SCCOD-RS constellations may represent one of the most energy-efficient SCCOD approaches.

Let us now compare the energy efficiency of three types of constellations: SCCOD-RS, SCSH, and SCOPT. Assume that message transmission in SCCOD-RS systems employs a

basic QAM constellation with spectral efficiency $R_f = 8$ bit/(s·Hz). For $R_c = 0.8$ and 0.9 , the spectral efficiency of SCCOD-RS becomes $R_{fc} = 6.4$ and 7.2 bit/(s·Hz), respectively.

Fig. 2 presents the dependences $P_{dem}(\rho_s)$ for SCCOD-RS, SCSH, and SCOPT constellations at $R_{fc} = 6.4$ (Fig. 2a) and 7.2 bit/(s·Hz) (Fig. 2b). The results are shown for two values of normalized signal duration: $n = 400$ and $n = 4000$.

a) $R_{fc} = 6.4$ bit/(s·Hz);

The results presented in Fig. 2 illustrate the differences in the mechanisms providing high transmission reliability for the considered types of constellations. In SCCOD-RS systems, high reliability is achieved through the transmission of codewords containing both information and parity symbols. One limitation of SCCOD-RS constellations is that the introduction of parity symbols reduces their spectral efficiency compared with the underlying signal constellations. Therefore, as illustrated in Fig. 2, the energy efficiency of SCCOD-RS constellations may be lower than that of SCSH constellations under the considered assumptions.

Fig. 2 also shows that increasing the spectral efficiency of SCCOD-RS communication systems generally requires an increase in the signal-to-noise ratio at the demodulator input and, consequently, an increase in transmitter power.

In the considered case, this increase amounts to approximately 3–3.5 dB. Relative to SCSH systems, the corresponding energy losses of SCCOD-RS are approximately 1–1.5 dB.

b) $R_{fc} = 7.2 \text{ bit}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{Hz})$

The SCSH constellation proposed by Shannon was long regarded as the only type of signal constellation capable of providing reliable communication while transmitting only information symbols through the communication channel. According to Shannon [4], communication systems employing such constellations could be regarded as “idealized” from the viewpoint of energy efficiency. However, as noted above, constellations possessing geometric properties similar to those of SCSH have not been employed in practical communication systems to date.

Fig. 2 also presents the dependences $P_{dem}(\rho_s)$ for a new class of constellations referred to as SCOPT. These constellations possess a property that Shannon [4] associated with the possibility of constructing energy-efficient communication systems: the minimum Euclidean distance between signals increases approximately proportionally to \sqrt{n} , where n is the normalized signal duration.

However, unlike SCSH constellations, the decision region in SCOPT is not an N -dimensional sphere. As shown in [9] and in Section III.B, it consists of a set of lower-dimensional regions, in particular two-dimensional regions. Consequently, SCOPT signals possess a composite structure. Such a structure may substantially simplify both signal generation and signal demodulation.

In addition, similarly to SCSH constellations, SCOPT may allow high transmission reliability to be achieved while transmitting only information symbols and without using

parity symbols. It follows from Fig. 2 that for relatively small normalized signal durations, $n = 400$, the energy efficiency of SCOPT is lower than that of SCCOD-RS and SCSH constellations.

However, as the signal duration increases, the energy efficiency of SCOPT may also increase substantially. As can be seen from Fig. 2, at $P_{dem}(\rho_s) = 10^{-10}$ and $n = 4000$, SCOPT constellations may provide an energy gain of approximately 2 dB and 3 dB relative to SCSH for spectral efficiencies $R_{fc} = 6.4$ and $7.2 \text{ bit}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{Hz})$, respectively.

One notable property of SCOPT is that increasing the normalized signal duration may reduce the required transmitter power while maintaining high transmission reliability. In the present paper, SCOPT constellations are considered for Gaussian communication channels. However, similar behavior may also be expected in multipath fading channels.

The possibility of constructing SCOPT-type constellations raises an interesting theoretical question concerning the applicability of the concept of the “Shannon limit” as a universal criterion for comparing the energy efficiency of communication systems. As noted in Section III.A, even for SCSH systems the term “Shannon limit” is, to some extent, conditional, since such systems have not been practically implemented.

Therefore, this concept may require additional clarification following the appearance of signal constellations whose energy efficiency can substantially exceed that of SCSH constellations.

V. ESTIMATION OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS USING SCOPT CONSTELLATIONS

Improving the energy efficiency of communication systems is important not only from a technical but also from an economic point of view. The communications industry is one of the global infrastructure components of modern civilization and affects virtually all areas of societal activity, including industry, transportation, science, culture, education, and information services.

The development of communication systems must ensure increased transmission reliability, reduced transmission

latency, and reduced energy consumption while maintaining high spectral efficiency. These requirements are relevant both for systems with high spectral efficiency, $R_f \geq 2$ bit/(s·Hz), and for systems with low spectral efficiency, $R_f < 1$ bit/(s·Hz). Equally important is the requirement for acceptable implementation complexity of communication systems. These characteristics are largely determined by the properties of the employed signal constellations.

One promising class of such constellations is represented by SCOPT constellations. At the same time, the development of similar energy-efficient constellations is required for communication systems of different purposes and for different types of channels, including wired, satellite, terrestrial, fixed, mobile, and multipath fading channels.

Modern communication systems consume enormous amounts of electrical energy. Therefore, even a relatively small improvement in energy efficiency may produce a significant global economic effect.

Let us estimate such an effect for communication systems employing SCOPT-type signal constellations that provide an energy gain of approximately 5–15 dB relative to the Shannon limit.

This gain is achieved by increasing signal duration while maintaining comparatively moderate normalized signal durations, substantially smaller than those required for SCCOD-LDPC systems, where codeword lengths may reach tens of thousands of symbols.

One of the fundamental references in the design of communication systems is Shannon's channel-capacity theorem, which determines the minimum signal-to-noise ratio required for reliable information transmission at a specified spectral efficiency. Practical communication systems generally exhibit lower energy efficiency than hypothetical SCSH systems and therefore possess certain energy losses relative to the Shannon limit.

The use of more advanced signal-formation methods, in particular SCOPT-type signal constellations, makes it possible to substantially reduce the required transmitter power. For a quantitative estimate of the global effect, let us assume that the total worldwide energy consumption of communication systems is $E_0 = 1100$ TWh/year, which

corresponds to an average continuous power of $P_0 = E_0/8760 \approx 126$ GW.

Assume further that the application of new signal constellations reduces the required transmitter power by X dB. Then, according to the logarithmic decibel scale, the new required power is determined by $P_1 = P_0 \cdot 10^{-X/10}$. Accordingly, the relative reduction in power and energy consumption is $\eta(X) = 1 - 10^{-X/10}$. The annual energy saving may therefore be written as $\Delta E = E_0(1 - 10^{-X/10})$, while the remaining energy consumption becomes $E_1 = E_0 \cdot 10^{-X/10}$.

To convert the energy gain into an economic effect, let us assume an average electricity price of $c = 0.10$ \$/kWh. Since $1 \text{ TWh} = 10^9 \text{ kWh}$, a saving of 1 TWh/year corresponds to approximately 0.1 billion USD/year. Consequently, the annual financial saving is determined by $\Delta C_{\text{year}} = 0.1 \cdot \Delta E$ billion USD/year, while the monthly saving is $\Delta C_{\text{month}} = \Delta C_{\text{year}}/12$.

The calculated results for representative values of the energy gain are presented in Table I:

Column 1 - **Energy Gain**

Column 2 - **Energy Reduction**

Column 3 - **Energy Saving (TWh/year)**

Column 4 - **Remaining Consumption (TWh/year)**

Column 5 - **Saving (billion USD/year)**

Column 6 - **Saving (billion USD/month)**

TABLE I. ESTIMATED GLOBAL ENERGY AND ECONOMIC EFFECT

1	2	3	4	5	6
5 dB	68 %	752	348	75	6
10 dB	90 %	990	110	99	8
15 dB	97 %	1065	35	106	9

The obtained results show that even a moderate reduction in the required transmitter power relative to the Shannon limit, for example by 5 dB, may lead to a significant global effect. In this case, the energy saving amounts to hundreds of TWh per year, which is equivalent to tens of gigawatts of average power and tens of billions of dollars in annual savings. As the energy gain increases to 10–15 dB, the resulting energy savings become comparable to the present-day energy consumption of the global communications infrastructure.

The presented estimates are illustrative and are intended to demonstrate the possible scale of the economic effect.

VI. CONCLUSION

One of the most important objectives of communication theory is the development of transmission methods providing high reliability, high spectral efficiency, and simultaneously high energy efficiency of communication systems. As noted above, the fundamental formulation of these problems and the principal ideas for their solution were established by Claude Shannon in the middle of the twentieth century.

As a result of his research, two fundamentally important conclusions were established:

1. High transmission reliability can be achieved through the use of signal constellations with large signal durations.
2. It is possible to construct special signal constellations providing arbitrarily high transmission reliability at limited transmitter power by increasing signal duration.

The development of the first of these ideas led to the intensive development of coding theory and to the creation of numerous SCCOD constellations.

The analysis performed in the present work shows that among the considered SCCOD types, comparatively high energy efficiency is achieved by SCCOD-RS constellations based on Reed–Solomon codes. It is shown that SCCOD-RS constellations provide high transmission reliability under different spectral-efficiency requirements. However, the necessity of transmitting parity symbols leads to the condition $R_c < 1$, which reduces the spectral efficiency of the communication system.

Shannon's second idea was associated with the possibility of constructing SCSH constellations intended for the transmission of only information symbols. Shannon regarded such systems as "idealized" from the viewpoint of energy efficiency.

The present analysis indicates that communication systems employing SCCOD-RS constellations may exhibit energy losses relative to SCSH on the order of approximately 3–5 dB, and that these losses increase with increasing spectral efficiency. It is also noted that practical engineering implementations of SCSH communication systems have not yet become available.

The paper considers a new approach to the construction of composite SCOPT signal constellations. This approach is based on Shannon's idea of increasing the minimum Euclidean distance through increasing signal duration and is supplemented by the use of a composite geometric signal structure. It is shown that the energy efficiency of SCOPT increases with increasing signal duration and may under certain assumptions provide higher estimated energy efficiency than SCSH constellations.

Another potentially important property of SCOPT is its comparatively low implementation complexity. The presented estimates suggest that, in terms of signal generation and demodulation complexity, communication systems employing SCOPT may be comparable to uncoded QAM systems.

The paper also presents an estimate of the economic effect associated with the use of energy-efficient signal constellations. It is shown that the application of SCOPT-type constellations may potentially lead to a substantial reduction in the energy consumption of the global communications infrastructure and provide annual savings of many billions of dollars in electricity costs.

It is noted that further development of SCOPT-type constellations appears promising both for communication systems with high spectral efficiency ($R_f > 2 \text{ bit}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{Hz})$) and for systems with low spectral efficiency ($R_f < 1 \text{ bit}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{Hz})$).

Such constellations may be of interest for wired, radio-relay, satellite, and multipath communication systems, including MIMO systems. In the author's opinion, further investigation of SCOPT-type signal constellations represents a promising direction.

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